

1 **Coexistence in the Mediterranean-Temperate transitional border: multi-century**
2 **dynamics of a mixed old-growth forest under global change**

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22 **Highlights**

- 23 •Historical shifts in forest dominance between temperate and sub-Mediterranean
- 24 species
- 25 •Recent *Fagus sylvatica* growth decline unprecedented in the last two hundred years
- 26 •Higher climate sensitivity of temperate *F. sylvatica* than oak species
- 27 •Oak species better suited to current environmental conditions

28

29 **Abstract**

30 Old-growth forests, particularly those located at the interface between different
31 bioregions, are unevaluable sources of long-term vegetation dynamics and historical
32 stand response to natural and anthropogenic disturbance. Although old-growth forest are
33 scarce, the information gathered studying them may assist forest ecosystem restoration
34 and management under forthcoming climate and land use changes.

35 We analysed how complementary dynamics of a mixed old-growth forest composed by
36 temperate (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Quercus petraea*) and submediterranean (*Quercus*
37 *pyrenaica*) tree species were driven in response to global changes in the last two centuries.

38 The old-growth forest, named El Hayedo de Montejo, is located at the interface between
39 the Mediterranean and temperate bioregions in the centre of the Iberian Peninsula. The
40 populations of temperate species growing in El Hayedo de Montejo (*F.sylvatica* and
41 *Q.petraea*) are at the dry and warm edges of their natural distribution area in Europe,
42 whereas the submediterranean species *Q. pyrenaica* is at the core of the distribution range.

43 In order to analyse the long-term dynamics, we developed basal area increment and
44 disturbance chronologies for each of the tree species under study. Furthermore, we
45 assessed the climate influence on tree growth during the most recent decades.

46 Our results reveal historical shifts in forest dominance (as reflected by growth) induced
47 by changes in climate and forest management between temperate and sub-Mediterranean
48 species. This was particularly noticeable for *F. sylvatica* and *Q. pyrenaica* the least and
49 most drought-tolerant species, respectively. A reduction in growth of *F. sylvatica*
50 unprecedented in the context of the last two hundred years was observed during the last
51 decades concurrent with forest densification and marked changes in climate. Conversely,
52 both oak species seem to be better suited to current environmental conditions as expressed
53 by increasing growth rates.

54 **1. Introduction**

55 Old-growth forests are scarce but still a relevant global carbon sink (Luyssaert et al. 2008)
56 and a source of genetic diversity (Mosseler et al. 2006). They are also essential
57 benchmarks for studying and understanding ecosystem processes in long-time scales
58 (e.g., D'Amato & Orwig 2008) and in the face of environmental change (Rackham 2008;
59 Messier et al. 2009). The value of old-growth forests is multiplied with increasing
60 marginality since populations at the limits of the species distribution conform the edge
61 for adaptation and evolution of plant species under forthcoming climate change (Hampe
62 & Petit 2005).

63 Given the rate of global and regional warming, climate conditions during the growing
64 season may challenge the tolerance and ability of marginal populations to locally adapt
65 and persist (Midgley et al. 2007; Moritz & Agudo 2013). Concretely, future enhancement
66 of dry conditions may induce changes in species dynamics of marginal mixed forests,
67 reduce the distribution area of species with lower drought-tolerance and/or force their
68 retreat to higher altitudes/latitudes, especially at the rear-edge of the distribution range
69 (Thuiller et al. 2005; Lenoir et al. 2008; Zimmermann et al. 2009; Czúcz et al. 2011;
70 Gómez-Aparicio et al. 2011; Vacchiano & Motta 2015; Hanewinkel et al. 2013).

71 Persistence of populations at the rear edge is particularly important as specific genetic
72 variables conferring local adaptation to strong abiotic stresses may foster the evolution
73 and maintenance of species as a whole (Lesica & Allendorf 1995); Aitken et al. 2008;
74 Hampe & Jump 2011). Currently and due to climate change, the conditions needed for
75 regeneration and establishment may be taking place more sparsely and scarcely than
76 before (Castro et al. 2004; Hampe & Petit 2005; Hampe & Jump 2011; Gea-Izquierdo et
77 al. 2015). Therefore, marginal populations of temperate species at the rear edge,
78 particularly old-growth, encode valuable long-term information not only on stand
79 dynamics, but also on species acclimation and tolerance to periods of dryness (Holt &
80 Keitt 2005; Piovesan et al. 2005; DiFilippo et al. 2015). Studies on species tolerance limits
81 are critical to forecast shifts in plant communities, which may result in tree species
82 persistence or, conversely, extirpation (Aitken et al. 2008).

83 Forest persistence largely depends on the ability of individual species to adapt their
84 structure and dominance during regimen shifts and mixed forests show evolutionary
85 advantages on climate change adaptation and persistence compared to monospecific (e.g.
86 Thompson et al. 2009; Ruiz-Benito et al. 2014). The biodiversity and associated climate
87 response heterogeneity contained in multispecies forests might provide an alternative
88 against ecosystem regimen shifts whilst monospecific systems may shift to a less desired
89 state (Elmqvist et al. 2003). Furthermore, some evidences point to a stress release by
90 inter-specific facilitation as well as enhanced species productivity in mixed compared to
91 monospecific forests under suboptimal site conditions (e.g. Pretzsch et al. 2013a, 2013b).

92 The Iberian Peninsula conforms the rear edge of the natural distribution of many
93 temperate and boreal tree species such as *Fagus sylvatica* L., *Quercus petraea*
94 (Mattuschka) Liebl., *Quercus robur* L., *Abies alba* Mill., *Pinus uncinata* Ram. and *Pinus*
95 *sylvestris* L. coexisting with more drought tolerant taxa (i.e., typical mediterranean

96 *Quercus* and *Pinus* spp.). Population growth rate is a sensitive and useful indicator on
97 incipient changes in dynamics (Dobbertin 2005) and significant changes in rear-edge
98 forests growth have been detected and linked to environmental dryness at the Iberian
99 Peninsula (e.g. Gutiérrez 1998; Peñuelas et al. 2008; Jump et al. 2006, Gea-Izquierdo et
100 al. 2014; Chen et al. 2015; Heres et al. 2014). However, recent changes in climate
101 inducing variations in forest growth have often been concurrent with changes in forest
102 management and distinguishing those effects is challenging (Peñuelas & Boada, 2003;
103 Peñuelas et al. 2008; Gea-Izquierdo et al. 2015).

104 In this context, the analysis of chronologies derived from old-growth forests provides a
105 unique opportunity to reconstruct forest history in response to climate and non-climatic
106 disturbances, including management (e.g., Piovesan et al. 2005). In an effort to
107 understand the dynamics of co-occurring tree species at the transitional border between
108 two bioregions coupled with the changes in climate, we investigate the historical
109 dynamics of an old-growth forest dominated by a combination of temperate species (*F.*
110 *sylvatica* and *Q. petraea*) and a sub-Mediterranean tree species (*Quercus pyrenaica*
111 Willd.). We focus on analysing the factors inducing changes in species growth and
112 performance, to detect potential shifts in species dominance at the stand level and,
113 particularly, how complementary dynamics of these three species was driven in response
114 to environmental changes in the last two centuries. We hypothesise that the species with
115 the lowest drought-tolerance (*F. sylvatica*) will show higher vulnerability to recent
116 enhancement in dry conditions, as expressed by reduced growth rates.

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120 2. Material and Methods

121 2.1 Site description

122 The study site, El Hayedo de Montejo (Montejo hereafter), is a natural old-growth beech-
123 oak forest of 125 ha located at the rear-edge distribution range of the two temperate
124 species at the Sistema Central of the Iberian Peninsula (41° 7'N; 3° 30' W) between
125 1,250-1,500 m a.s.l (**Figure 1**). Montejo is a forest located at the interface between the
126 Mediterranean and the Temperate bioregions (Hernández Bermejo et al. 1983) where
127 typical temperate species such as *Fagus sylvatica* (FaSy hereafter) and *Quercus petraea*
128 (QuPe hereafter) coexist with typical sub-Mediterranean species such as *Quercus*
129 *pyrenaica* (QuPy). Documents dating back to the 13th century made already reference to
130 the existence and management of the mixed beech-oak Montejo forest (Ubieto Arteta
131 1959). The forest has historically been exploited for firewood and used as a resting place
132 for livestock. However this traditional management almost disappeared during the 20th
133 century along with a marked decrease in the number of inhabitants (Pardo & Gil 2005).
134 Since the 1960's decade, cattle management is forbidden in the forest, although the
135 protection of the area was effective only since 1974 (Pardo 2000). Because of its great
136 ecological importance, in 2005 the forest was declared a biosphere reserve where human
137 intervention and access is very limited (Gil et al. 2010).

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143 **Figure 1.** Location (top-left) and climogram (top right) of El Hayedo de Montejo beech-
144 oak forest. Mean monthly temperature and monthly sum precipitation are calculated as
145 anomalies for the period 1950-2012. Bottom picture shows the limits of the forest and the
146 distribution of the forest inventory plots.

147

148 The climate is Mediterranean continental (Oromediterranean humid according to Rivas
149 Martínez 1987) with two precipitation maxima in spring (May) and autumn (November)
150 (**Figure 1**). The mean annual temperature is around 9.5 °C and the annual sum of
151 precipitation is 900 mm with a summer dry period spanning 1.8 months approximately
152 (Gil et al. 2010). The soil has been classified as humic cambisol (Pardo et al. 1997) and
153 the horizon A reaches 50 cm of depth on average which allows to store water during dry
154 periods so that temperate species such as QuPe and FaSy can thrive. QuPy is the most
155 drought-tolerant species among the three, hence more adapted to sub-Mediterranean
156 climatic conditions, whereas the two temperate species, particularly FaSy, require higher
157 moisture levels during the summer period (Lendzion & Leuschner 2008). QuPe is
158 considered more-drought tolerant than FaSy (Raftoyannis & Radoglou 2002; Aranda et

159 al. 2005; Lenzion & Leuschner 2008) and FaSy more shade tolerant than QuPe (von
160 Lüpke 1998).

161 ***2.2 Growth and climate data***

162 Sampling took place during spring of 2013. At least, 20 dominant or co/dominant trees
163 including different size classes were sampled per species. Diameter at breast height
164 (DBH) and total height were measured in every tree and two cores of 5 mm of diameter
165 were taken. Cores were air-dried and sanded until ring boundaries were clearly visible
166 under a stereo-microscope. Samples of each species were visually crossdated following
167 Stokes & Smiley (1968) and uncrossdatable samples were discarded from further
168 analysis. The ring-width of each sample was measured with a precision of 0.01mm using
169 a Linntab 6 (RINNTECH) measuring device. The correct dating of every sample was re-
170 checked using COFECHA (Holmes 1983). Individual tree-ring series were converted to
171 Basal Area Increments (BAI) to avoid age-related trends in non-juvenile ring-width
172 measurements (Biondi & Qaedan 2008). The conversion of the individual ring-width
173 measurements to individual-BAI series follows the equation:

$$174 \text{BAI}_t = \pi (wt^2 + 2 w_t R_t)$$

175 where w_t is the annual radial increment and R_t is the stem radius.

176 The final species chronologies were built by averaging all individual BAI measurements
177 of the same species. The statistical quality of each chronology was checked via Expressed
178 Population Signal (EPS; Wigley et al. 1984) considering in the calculation more than one
179 core per tree. A threshold value of $\text{EPS} > 0.85$ was considered reliable. Age of trees at
180 coring height was estimated proportional to the measured DBH and the inner 20 rings
181 measured (Rozas 2003).

182 In addition, number of trees per hectare as well as diameter distribution for each of the
183 tree species and for the total number of species were retrieved from detailed forest
184 inventories carried out in 1994, 2005 and 2015 (Vélez Olalde 2016).

185 High-resolution and homogenized gridded data of daily climate over Europe (E-OBS;
186 Haylock et al. 2008) was chosen as input climate data for the assessment of the influence
187 of climate on tree growth. A $1^{\circ}\times 1^{\circ}$ cell of mean monthly temperature and total
188 precipitation for the period 1950-2012 was extracted for the studied site. Additionally,
189 data from a nearby observatory was available for sunshine duration (SS) and percentage
190 of cloud cover (CC) records for the same period (Sanchez Lorenzo et al. 2007, 2013).

191 *2.3 Analyses of the relationships between environmental variables, disturbances and* 192 *growth*

193 Each species chronology was smoothed using centred moving averages with different
194 window sizes and then correlated across species using R software (R Core Team, 2015).
195 The similarity among BAI chronologies in the different frequency domains was addressed
196 by Pearson's correlations. Bootstrapped significance levels were assessed using R-
197 package 'boot' (Canty & Ripley 2016).

198 The potential differences in growth among species during the recent decades were tested
199 using a Kolmogórov-Smirnov paired test. The two periods selected were delimited based
200 on the exclusion of cattle and limitation of forest activities in 1961 and the significant
201 forest densification (understood as a significant increase in the number of stems per
202 hectare) detected from 1994 onwards as described by Gil et al. (2010).

203 Differences in climatic sensitivity among species were also investigated. Each BAI
204 chronology was correlated with monthly and seasonal mean temperature, precipitation,

205 SS and CC from the previous and current year of growth using R software (R Core Team,
206 2015) from previous year April to current year October.

207 Disturbance chronologies were built using tree-ring width to identify historical abrupt
208 positive (releases) or negative (suppressions) changes in growth in each species (Nowacki
209 & Abrams 1997). This approach minimizes the long-term growth trends and interannual
210 growth variations usually driven by climate, while enhances decadal abrupt and sustained
211 radial-growth changes characteristic of forest disturbances. Growth changes (GC) were
212 calculated for the individual tree-ring series using a 10-year running window as either
213 positive (PGC) or negative (NGC) growth changes:

$$214 \%GC = [(M_2 - M_1) / M_1] * 100$$

215 where M_1 is preceding 10-yr mean and M_2 is subsequent 10-yrs mean (for further
216 methodological details on the calculation, the reader is referred to Gea-Izquierdo &
217 Cañellas 2014). Site disturbance chronologies per species were constructed by averaging
218 the individual disturbances series (Camarero et al. 2011). A minimum GC of 25% was
219 established to depict canopy disturbances. Furthermore, more than 50% of the individual
220 trees displaying the same growth changes was considered a stand-wise disturbance.

221 **3. Results**

222 ***3.1 Forest growth during the last 300 years***

223 The QuPe chronology was the longest one spanning the period 1623-2012, whereas FaSy
224 was the shortest reaching back 1750 (*Supplementary Table 1*). QuPe individuals were
225 also the most productive for the common reliable period 1810-2012 reaching a mean
226 annual BAI of 28.1 cm², whereas growth of QuPy was the lowest (24.3 cm²). In terms of
227 height, FaSy trees were higher (21.0 m) than oaks; but the difference was only significant
228 with the smallest QuPy trees (see *Supplementary Figure 1*). The differences in height

229 between the two oak species were non-significant (18.5 and 17.2 m for QuPe and QuPy,
230 respectively).

231 The comparison of the estimated individual-tree age revealed similarities in the age
232 distribution of the sampled trees among species. The three species depicted bimodal
233 distributions of estimated tree age being the first mode in the early 17th (both oak species)
234 or 18th (FaSy) centuries and the second mode in the second half of the 19th century for all
235 the three species (*Supplementary Figure 2*). The latter, was the age class with the largest
236 number of individuals for FaSy and QuPy, while QuPe showed the maximum number of
237 trees during the first half of the 17th century. QuPe and QuPy presented an older group of
238 trees than FaSy. Particularly, the main group of sampled QuPe trees were dated along the
239 16th century and the first half of the 17th century (*Supplementary Figure 2*).

240

241 **Figure 2.** **a)** Basal area increment chronologies (BAI) of *Quercus petraea* (QuPe),
242 *Quercus pyrenaica* (QuPy) and *Fagus sylvatica* (FaSy); **b)** correlation among
243 chronologies for the common period 1810-2012 in different time-domains after pre-
244 filtering the time-series with increasing size of the moving-average window. Shading in
245 **a)** corresponds to the confidence intervals of the standard error of the mean.
246 Discontinuous line in **b)** corresponds to 95% significance level.

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251 The analysis of the BAI chronologies revealed a clear increase in growth for *Quercus spp.*
252 during the last two centuries, particularly pronounced since 1850 (**Figure 3**). Both oak
253 species displayed a fairly constant BAI ranging between 10 and 20 cm²/year up to 1850,
254 steadily increasing thereafter up to values over 30 cm²/year in the 21st century. QuPe
255 growth was slightly greater during the last 5 decades than QuPy, reaching values over 40
256 cm²/year. In contrast, the BAI chronology of FaSy did not show a long-term increase in
257 productivity along the last two centuries but multidecadal variations. FaSy reached the
258 maximum of 30 cm²/year during the second half of the 19th century coinciding with a
259 period of lower productivity of oak species, particularly QuPy. Such a trend shifted after
260 1930, when FaSy BAI started to decrease simultaneously to the oak species growth
261 enhancement, reaching the minimum values during the last two decades.

262 The observed differences in the BAI evolution across species are further summarized in
263 **Figure 2b**. The significant positive correlation between QuPe and QuPy revealed the
264 synchronic pattern of tree growth between oaks in all frequency domains (i.e., from
265 interannual variations to long-term trends). In contrast, FaSy displayed a poor agreement
266 with the oak species in all frequency domains, particularly with the sub-Mediterranean
267 QuPy. Only the correlation between FaSy and QuPe at interannual time scales is
268 significant, revealing some similarities in the annual growth between the two temperate
269 species.

270 The marked decreasing growth trend displayed by FaSy since the mid-1980s (**Figure 2**)
271 translated into a significant reduction in population growth since 1994 respect to the
272 previous decades (**Supplementary Figure 3**) while non-significant differences were
273 found in QuPy and QuPe population growth for the same period.

274

275 **3.2 Growth-climate relationships**

276 The correlations of BAI chronologies with precipitation, temperature, CC and SS
 277 evidenced a higher sensitivity of FaSy to climate, particularly to dryness (i.e, warm, dry
 278 and sunny conditions), than QuPe and QuPy (**Figure 3**). The only common climate signal
 279 to all three species was a significant negative impact on growth of current year October
 280 temperature. Neither QuPe nor QuPy displayed a response to temperature and
 281 precipitation typical from trees growing in drought-limited environments, being QuPy the
 282 least sensitive species. In contrast, FaSy showed evidences of being limited (i.e. stressed)
 283 by previous and current year higher summer temperatures and SS and low moisture.

284 **Figure 3.** Climate-growth relationships of *Quercus petraea* (QuPe), *Quercus pyrenaica*
 285 (QuPy) and *Fagus sylvatica* (FaSy) with monthly mean temperature (T) and precipitation
 286 sum (P) (**a, c, e**) and with monthly sunshine hours (SS) and percentage of cloud cover
 287 (CC) (**b, d, f**) for the previous (upper case letters) and current (low-case letters) year of
 288 growth. The highest seasonal correlations found are also shown only when significant.
 289 Dashes and dotted lines represent 95 and 99% significance levels.

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292 Summer temperatures exerted a significant negative effect on FaSy growth during
293 previous and current year of growth, while the effect of precipitation during the early
294 summer months was significant and positive. The response of FaSy to previous (JUN-
295 JUL) and current (Jun) summer and SS (negative) is concurrent with the relations found
296 with temperature: sunny conditions in May and cloudy conditions in June and July
297 (usually associated to lower temperatures) positively affected next year tree growth.
298 During the current year of growth, FaSy was positively influenced by cloudy conditions
299 in spring and early summer.

300 The temperate oak species QuPe, displayed a significant positive correlation with late
301 summer to autumn temperature of previous year (AUG-NOV), whereas no significant
302 correlation with precipitation was found. Similarly to FaSy, QuPe was positively
303 influenced by cloudy conditions during the previous year early summer and current year
304 spring.

305 QuPy displayed significant negative correlations with February and March temperatures
306 of the current year of growth. Precipitation of previous MAY-JUL exerted the most
307 significant limitation on growth. QuPy did not show significant response to SS and CC,
308 except for a positive influence on tree growth of previous year May (November) sunny
309 (cloudy) conditions.

310 ***3.3 Forest history***

311 The analysis of growth changes during the last centuries revealed that stand-wise changes
312 (i.e, growth change is detected in more than 50% of sampled trees) occurred more often
313 in FaSy than in the oak species (***Figure 4***). While for QuPe and QuPy we identified few
314 growth changes affecting more than half of the sampled individuals, for FaSy most of the
315 observed growth changes during the last 200 years affected a large proportion of the

316 sampled trees. The observed growth change shared by all tree species is concentrated in
 317 the second half of the 19th century. This period started with one of the driest lustrum up
 318 to 1900 (Domínguez Castro et al. 2012) that took place between 1840 and 1850
 319 approximately. During this period the three species showed a slight reduction in growth
 320 followed by a positive growth change (PGC) right after that period. This PGC was the
 321 most relevant one for QuPe in the context of the last 200 years and affected a large
 322 proportion of the sampled trees. The same PGC was observed in FaSy although less
 323 pronounced, whereas in QuPy the growth change was not that evident, non-significant
 324 and just observed in few of the sampled trees.

325 **Figure 4** Comparison of mean growth changes (GC) and percentage of trees affected by
 326 the GC > 50% for *Quercus petraea* (QuPe), *Quercus pyrenaica* (QuPy) and *Fagus*
 327 *sylvatica* (FaSy). Relevant historical perturbations are highlighted: dry periods (yellow
 328 shading, based on Brunet et al 2007a,b; Domínguez-Castro et al. 2012; Gil et al. 2010);
 329 thinning (grey shading) and changes in forest management (black line) (Gil et al. 2010)

330

331

332 The PGC in the 1860s was followed by a marked negative growth change in FaSy while
333 *Quercus spp* did not show marked decreases in growth in the last 200 years. Similarly,
334 throughout the 20th century, FaSy displayed several significant negative growth changes
335 not observed in QuPy and QuPe. The only positive and significant growth change along
336 the 20th century affecting FaSy took place after the last dry period at the end of 1940s and
337 the last thinning at the beginning of 1950s (Gil et al. 2010). The later event was also
338 related to PGC in QuPe (though non-significant) but again no effect was observed in the
339 less sensitive QuPy trees. The largest negative growth anomaly detected in the last 200
340 years was an abrupt growth reduction in FaSy since the 1990s onwards and concurrent
341 with a number of observed changes in the meteorological series of Montejo but also with
342 profound changes in forest structure as a consequence of forest protection (**Figure 5;**
343 **Figure 6**). Such a negative growth change was also observed in QuPe and QuPy, though
344 less pronounced than in FaSy and non-significant (**Figure 4**, see also **Supplementary Fig**
345 **3**).

346 Particularly remarkable are also the antiphase relationships between the oak species and
347 FaSy during the extreme dry summer of 2000 and the largely more detrimental effect of
348 2005 summer drought in FaSy growth than in the growth of the two oak species (**Figure**
349 **5**).

350 According to the forest inventory data, the number of trees per hectare and particularly
351 the basal area have generally increased in Montejo since 1994 (**Figure 6a-b**). However,
352 only FaSy displays a continuous increase in the number of trees per hectare up to 2015
353 due to a higher recruitment rate (**Figure 6c**). In turn, QuPe and QuPy display an increase
354 in the number of stems in 2005 respect to 1994 but and slightly decrease in the forest
355 inventory of 2015.

356 **Figure 5** Changes in Basal Area Increment (BAI) of the three tree species since 1961.
 357 Interannual variations on main climatic features are also shown: March-June sunshine
 358 duration (SS; yellow), June-July temperature (T; orange), June-July precipitation (P;
 359 blue) and March-June cloud cover (CC; grey). Vertical lines mark reported changes in
 360 trend of mean temperature (orange; Brunet et al. 2007a); sunshine duration and cloud
 361 cover (yellow and grey, respectively; Sanchez Lorenzo et al. 2007, 2013) and frequency
 362 of warm spells (red; Brunet et al 2007b). Yellow shading highlights exceptionally long
 363 summer-drought spells recorded in Montejo (Gil et al. 2010). All series in anomalies
 364 respect to the 1987-2012 mean.

365

366 **Figure 6.** Evolution of the observed (a) density of trees (number of trees per hectare) and (b)
 367 diameter-frequency distribution per hectare and c) number of trees per diameter class in Montejo
 368 forest by species group and for the total of species. Based on forest inventory data from 1994,
 369 2005, 2015.

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372 **4. Discussion**

373 *4.1 Long-term dynamics show complementary niche optimization*

374 Although historical evidences dating back to the 14th century described the existence of
375 QuPe and FaSy trees in Montejo (Saez, 1956; Ubieto Arteta 1959; Fernández García
376 1985), we could only estimate ages of FaSy up to 300 years old based on the sampled
377 trees. In contrast, we found individuals from both oak species displaying estimated ages
378 greater than 400 years old, even above 500 years old in QuPe trees. Some documental
379 evidences report the felling of large beech trees at the end of the 19th century (Pardo &
380 Gil 2005), which could be a reason underlying the observed maximum ages.

381 Mid-1800s was a period of major socio-economic changes in the Iberian Peninsula,
382 including two disentailments, which likely intensified exploitation and modified the
383 structure of many forests in Spain (Valbuena-Carabaña et al. 2010). This, together with
384 major climate changes, has been suggested as an explanation for the regeneration peak
385 (or maximum tree ages) in the mid-1800s for various Iberian forests including oak
386 woodlands (e.g. Gea-Izquierdo & Cañellas 2014; Gea-Izquierdo et al. 2014, 2015).
387 During this period, FaSy exhibited a higher growth rate than oak species, especially than
388 QuPy, which showed a marked antiphase growth respect to FaSy. Although Montejo
389 forest was excluded from the disentailments, grazing and pruning were taking place, and
390 usually oak withstood higher impacts due to the cattle preference of acorns over beechnuts
391 (Pardo & Gil 2005; Gil et al. 2010). This period of higher growth in FaSy than in QuPy
392 was also climatically characterized by cooler temperatures associated to the end of the
393 so-called Little Ice Age (LIA; Lamb 1977; Mann et al. 1998, 2009). In central Spain, the
394 end of LIA was characterized by lower temperatures and scarcer droughts in spring and
395 summer compared to the preceding and subsequent centuries (Domínguez Castro et al.
396 2008). Therefore, climate during this period was more humid and cooler, favouring the

397 growth of temperate species, which may explain the higher productivity of FaSy
398 individuals and to a lesser extent QuPe, compared to those of QuPy. FaSy is able to
399 quickly dominate the other coexisting forest tree species under favourable (cold, moist)
400 local conditions (Ellenberg 1988; Lupke 1998), partly due to an earlier budburst and leave
401 unfolding compared to QuPe and QuPy (Aranda et al. 1996; Aranda et al. 2005). In
402 contrast, QuPy displays the shortest growing period and the most delayed budbreak and
403 leave unfolding among the three species (Aranda & Pardos 1996). Thus, under
404 climatically favourable conditions for temperate species (FaSy and QuPe), QuPy will
405 most likely be outcompeted by FaSy and QuPe, which would limit its growth. Conversely,
406 dry periods should favour QuPy against FaSy and QuPe, being FaSy the most negatively
407 affected. Hence, our results support the hypothesis of complementary long-term dynamics
408 along a species drought-tolerance gradient.

409 ***4.2 Forest resistance and resilience to historical disturbances***

410 During the 18th and 19th centuries, pruning with a rotation period between 15 and 30 years
411 was relatively common at the area where Montejo forest is located, particularly affecting
412 oak spp. (Pardo & Gil 2005). However, no periodic growth depression affecting a large
413 portion of the sampled trees is observed in the disturbance chronologies, which could be
414 due to oak spp. resistance to such events (e.g., Götmark & Kiffer 2014; Merlin et al. 2015)
415 or to the described low intensity of the management activities (Gil et al. 2010).
416 Conversely, some perturbation induced synchronous decadal growth changes among
417 species. The most prominent stand-wise PGC observed in the context of the last 200 years
418 took place after the dry decade of 1850s in which the temperate species, particularly
419 QuPe, were more productive after the dry period. Old individuals of QuPe have been
420 described as resilient to dry episodes (Merlin et al. 2015), although the resulting increase
421 in productivity was transient as found in other mixed forest (Cavin et al. 2013).

422 Remarkably, the most pronounced stand-wise negative growth change was observed at
423 the end of the 20th century and affected particularly FaSy. Such a growth decrease,
424 significant for FaSy, was concurrent with changes in climate leading to global regime
425 shifts (Reid et al. 2016). At the Iberian Peninsula the described climate changes were
426 characterized by a warming trend since 1973 unprecedented in the context of the last 150
427 year (Brunet et al. 2007a), sunnier conditions since 1980s (the so-called “brightening
428 phase”; Sanchez Lorenzo et al. 2007, 2013); and an increased number of warm-spells
429 since the 1990s (Brunet et al. 2007b). Simultaneously, the cessation of forest exploitation
430 activities and the protection of Montejo were effective in the mid-1970s, concretely since
431 1974 (Pardo & Gil 2005). Severe protection in natural areas is known to promote forest
432 densification and enhanced competition for resources (Linares et al. 2010; Gómez-
433 Aparicio et al. 2011). According to the forest inventory data, forest density has increased
434 in Montejo since 1994. Despite, showing a higher regeneration compared to QuPe and
435 QuPy, FaSy displays a gradual and significant growth reduction, which is usually
436 described as a clear symptom of tree decay preceding mortality in many trees species,
437 including beech (Gillner et al. 2013; Wurde et al. 2007, 2008). Although it is not possible
438 to experimentally verify and unequivocally attribute the observed long-term growth
439 changes to either biotic (competition) or abiotic (climate) factors, the greater climatic
440 sensitivity observed in FaSy and the large number of works reporting climate-induce
441 FaSy gradual growth reduction under dry conditions (Gutierrez 1988; Piutti & Cescatti
442 1997; Jump et al. 2006; Di Filippo et al. 2007; Piovesan et al. 2008) underlines climate
443 change as a relevant factor of the recent FaSy growth decline. Thus, our results suggest
444 that despite the remarkably forest resilience to natural and anthropogenic disturbances
445 (i.e., short events), long-term gradual changes such as the enhanced competition and
446 changes in climate (i.e., enhanced dryness) increasingly constrain FaSy growth at

447 Montejo, which could have negative implications for the species, particularly for the old
448 trees, in the near future.

449 ***4.2 Dynamics under recent climate change***

450 The observed greater climatic sensitivity of FaSy over *Quercus spp.* has been previously
451 described by other authors (Scharnweber et al. 2011; Bontemps et al. 2012; Cavin et al.
452 2013). Both temperate species, FaSy and QuPe, are expected to experience a strong
453 limitation by summer conditions on tree growth (Leuschner et al. 2001; Lebourgeois et
454 al. 2005; Jump et al. 2006; Piovesan et al. 2008), particularly when compared with more
455 drought-tolerant sub-mediterranean species (Corcuera et al 2002) like QuPy. However, in
456 Montejo forest, only FaSy clearly showed the negative summer impact on tree growth
457 expected for a species with low tolerance to drought. QuPe has been described to resist
458 adverse climatic conditions and extreme events better and occupy the ecological spaces
459 left by the less-drought tolerant FaSy (Ellenberg 1988). Among other functional
460 acclimation processes, FaSy tends to down-regulate photosynthesis earlier than QuPe to
461 avoid cavitation (Peterken & Mountford 1996; Leuschner et al. 2001; Raftoyannis &
462 Radoglou 2002; Bréda et al. 2006). Closing stomata during summer lowers the carbon
463 gain and as a consequence lag-effects are usually enhanced (Cochard et al. 2001;
464 Bréda et al. 2006). FaSy radial growth is theoretically not as dependent on previous
465 year carbon reserves as oak species, since stem growth starts after budbreak (Michelot
466 et al. 2012). However, in our results FaSy showed greater dependency on previous
467 year climate than oak, pointing to increased growth limitation likely induced by
468 climate (Chen et al. 2015).

469 In contrast, the climate response of the two oak species showed scarce significant lag-
470 effects. Under non moisture-limited conditions QuPy shows a poor sensitivity to climate
471 (Gea-Izquierdo & Cañellas 2014; González-González et al. 2014; 2015) and growth is

472 usually more dependent on tree size and competition than climate (Fernández-de-Uña et
473 al. 2015). However, under constraining climatic conditions inducing summer water stress,
474 QuPy shows a high sensitivity to climate, and particularly moisture availability
475 (Hernández-Santana et al. 2008; Gea-Izquierdo & Cañellas 2014). QuPe, displays a
476 highly variable climate sensitivity even at the dry and warm edges of the species natural
477 distribution (Martínez-Sancho et al. *submitted*). Our results support the hypothesis of a
478 greater climate-induced growth limitation of FaSy, the less drought tolerant species,
479 whereas the lower vulnerability to drought of QuPy was expressed as a low sensitivity to
480 climate and absence of negative growth changes. QuPy displays a delayed resumption
481 and faster earlywood development than QuPe and FaSy to avoid both, spring frost and
482 summer drought (Perez-de-Lis et al. 2016). In turn, QuPy is less competitive under more
483 mesic conditions (Aranda et al. 1996). According to our results, QuPe is also well suited
484 for current environmental conditions. The difference might be related to the ability of
485 ring-porous species such as oak to adjust their anatomical traits in order to avoid possible
486 drought damages, whereas the diffuse porous FaSy quickly close stomata to avoid
487 embolism (Barbaroux and Bréda 2002; Martínez-Sancho et al. *submitted*). During
488 moisture-limited episodes, oak trees tend to produce more but smaller rather than fewer
489 and bigger vessels, avoiding drought damages but ensuring water supply (Fonti & García-
490 González, 2008; Gea-Izquierdo et al., 2012; Perez-de-Lis et al. 2016; Martínez Sancho et
491 al *under review*)

492 Interestingly, our analysis also revealed a high sensitivity of FaSy to incoming solar
493 radiation during summer. It remains rather unclear whether FaSy, a shade-tolerant
494 species, grows better under partial (Petritan et al. 2007) or full light (Van Couwenberghe
495 et al. 2013). In Mediterranean-type ecosystems, solar radiation is a stress factor
496 particularly during summer, that may produce photoinhibition (Gómez-Aparicio et al.

497 2006) and enhanced water stress (e.g. through high vapour pressure deficit) that
498 imbalance gas exchange and plant assimilation (Aranda et al. 2005). According to our
499 results, FaSy growth is not only hampered by the summer high temperature and low
500 precipitation but also by incoming solar radiation.

501 **5. Conclusion**

502 In this study we investigate the dynamics during the last two centuries of three co-
503 occurring tree species forming a rich and diverse ecosystem in a unique mixed old-growth
504 forest at the transitional border between the Mediterranean and the temperate bioregions
505 at the centre of the Iberian Peninsula. The changes in climate coupled to a long-lasting
506 anthropogenic influence on the territory have played a determinant role in the species
507 composition, stand structure and interspecific dynamics of this forest on a region where
508 similar mixed forests have disappeared likely as a consequence of intense forest use and
509 livestock management since the Middle Ages.

510 Our results reflect antiphase growth dynamics between a temperate (FaSy) and the sub-
511 Mediterranean species (QuPy), but similar between QuPy and the temperate oak (QuPe).
512 The growth dynamics and climate sensitivity of the three co-occurring species at Montejo
513 can be explained by their position within a drought-tolerance gradient, being FaSy the
514 least drought tolerant. Changes in climate and forest management have induced historical
515 shifts in forest dominance (as expressed by growth rates) and a recent reduction in growth
516 of FaSy unprecedented in the context of the last two hundred years. This could portend
517 negative consequences not only for the persistence of FaSy at the rear-edge but also for
518 Montejo forest persistence under projected changes in climate. Interestingly, the analysis
519 of the growth changes revealed that not only the submediterranean QuPy but also the
520 temperate oak species QuPe seem to be well suited for current local environmental
521 conditions. Indeed, QuPe displayed higher growth rates than QuPy during the last decades,

522 despite being a temperate species. The anthropogenic influence played an historical role
523 shaping the composition and structure of Montejo forest and may have partly influenced
524 the observed growth variations. In this sense, vulnerability of FaSy to current climate
525 conditions may have been (and could further be) enhanced by the increasing forest
526 densification, which therefore should be taken into consideration when applying
527 conservation policies under climate change.

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